

ADAPTIVE INTELLIGENCE OF THE TEACHER AS A CONDITION FOR THE
SUCCESSFUL INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES INTO HIGHER
EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada ta'limning raqamli transformatsiyasi sharoitida pedagog shaxsining eng muhim sifatlaridan biri sifatida adaptiv intellekt tushunchasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Raqamli texnologiyalarni ta'lim jarayoniga muvaffaqiyatli integratsiya qilish nafaqat texnik vositalardan foydalanish darajasiga, balki pedagogning yangi sharoitlarga moslasha bilish qobiliyatiga, kasbiy barqarorlikni saqlashiga, innovatsion metodlarni qo'llashiga va o'quvchilarning bilish faoliyatini rag'batlantira olishiga ham bog'liq ekani ta'kidlanadi. Adaptiv intellektning asosiy komponentlari va ularning pedagogik amaliyotdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: adaptiv intellekt, pedagog, raqamli texnologiyalar, ta'limning raqamli transformatsiyasi, innovatsion o'qitish metodlari, kasbiy barqarorlik, bilish faoliyati.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается понятие адаптивного интеллекта как важнейшего качества личности педагога в условиях цифровой трансформации образования. Подчеркивается, что успешная интеграция цифровых технологий в образовательный процесс зависит не только от уровня владения техническими средствами, но и от способности педагога гибко адаптироваться к новым условиям, сохранять профессиональную устойчивость, применять инновационные методы и стимулировать познавательную активность обучающихся. Анализируются ключевые компоненты адаптивного интеллекта и их значение в педагогической практике.

Ключевые слова: адаптивный интеллект, педагог, цифровые технологии, цифровая трансформация образования, инновационные методы обучения, профессиональная устойчивость, когнитивная активность.

Abstract. The article examines the concept of adaptive intelligence as one of the most essential qualities of a teacher's personality in the context of the digital transformation of education. It is emphasized that the successful integration of digital technologies into the educational process depends not only on the level of technical proficiency, but also on the teacher's ability to flexibly adapt to new conditions, maintain professional stability, apply innovative methods, and stimulate students' cognitive activity. The key components of adaptive intelligence and their significance in pedagogical practice are analyzed.

Key words: adaptive intelligence, teacher, digital technologies, digital transformation of education, innovative teaching methods, professional resilience, cognitive activity.

Введение

The emerging era of digitalization requires continuous lifelong learning, with education becoming more interactive and personalized, while teaching approaches are being updated and new

technical methods are introduced. Digital learning tools entered widespread use with the advent of mobile devices at the very beginning of the 21st century. This circumstance contributes to the development of a qualitatively new educational process and, as stated in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020, No. UP-6079 “On the Approval of the Strategy ‘Digital Uzbekistan–2030’ and Measures for Its Effective Implementation,” sets renewed requirements for the content of teacher training.

Modern society is experiencing a stage of intensive digitalization that affects all areas of human activity. Education is no exception: digital technologies are becoming an integral part of the learning process, offering new forms of interaction, assessment tools, and resources for self-education. However, the effectiveness of their application directly depends on the professional readiness of teachers. Today, the teaching community faces the task not only of mastering digital tools but also of learning to use them creatively. As N. P. Dutko notes, the effective use of digital technologies in education makes learning more flexible, personalized, and interactive [1]. At the same time, adaptive intelligence plays a crucial role—an integrative quality of the individual that reflects the teacher’s ability to respond flexibly to changes, act successfully in unstable conditions, and find optimal solutions in new situations.

Since the 1980s, digital technologies in the field of education have been studied, initially associated with the emergence of personal computers and the Internet. However, the term “digital learning” began to be widely used only in the 2000s, thanks to the development of mobile devices. According to A. S. Stepanova-Bykova, digital learning involves the organization of the educational process through the use of digital educational resources, with e-learning occupying an important place [2].

Moreover, to this day, there is no single approach in science to defining this concept: the studies of I. M. Osmolovskaya and other scholars show that digital learning can be understood as online courses, as a learning process using information and communication technologies, or as electronic educational materials [3]. Other approaches to organizing the educational process in this context should also be noted. For example, K. Head suggested the use of phones in school classes as early as 2002 so that children could independently find information and actively participate in the educational process [4]. Research also describes the positive experience of using digital technologies in pedagogical universities, which increases the effectiveness of student learning.

An analysis of modern scientific research shows that over the past 15 years, pedagogical science has made significant progress in integrating digital technologies into the learning process. According to M. Yu. Balina, the pandemic significantly accelerated this process, forcing universities to quickly adapt to new challenges and to seek effective methods of online learning [5]. In his studies, M. Yasir writes that pedagogical universities are actively implementing digital technologies, training teachers and students in new educational formats, and monitoring the quality of educational activities [6]. Within the framework of this work, the most attractive are pedagogical theories related to the organization of personalized learning in pedagogical institutions, as they are rapidly gaining popularity. Supporting the ideas of R. Copes, we believe that they concern the organization of individualized learning for a large group of future teachers [7].

The term “adaptive intelligence” is actively used in psychology and pedagogy to denote the ability of an individual to build productive behavior in conditions of uncertainty and dynamics. According to R. Sternberg (Sternberg, 2019), adaptive intelligence presupposes a person’s ability to survive and develop in a rapidly changing environment while effectively using available resources.

In pedagogical activity, adaptive intelligence manifests itself through:

Cognitive flexibility – readiness to acquire new knowledge and restructure problem-solving approaches;

Emotional resilience – the ability to remain calm and constructive during the implementation of innovations;

Communication skills – the ability to establish dialogue with students in the digital environment;

Creativity – the search for non-standard methodological solutions using digital technologies.

These qualities enable teachers to successfully integrate digital tools without compromising the quality of education.

Methods of Solution.

The intensive implementation of digital technologies in education creates both new opportunities and challenges. Among them, the following can be highlighted:

- The necessity of continuous knowledge renewal – the digital environment requires lifelong self-education.

- The risk of digital inequality – not all learners have equal access to modern technologies.

- Information overload – it is essential for the teacher to be able to filter and structure large volumes of data.

- The changing role of the teacher – the teacher is no longer the sole source of knowledge but becomes a moderator of the educational process.

In these conditions, it is adaptive intelligence that enables the teacher to maintain productivity, apply innovations in the interests of students, and find a balance between traditional and modern forms of learning. Considering the subject of our research, the following methodological approaches have been identified to obtain a holistic characterization of the studied process: the systemic, learner-centered, and activity-competence-based approaches.

The essence of the systemic approach in the use of adaptive learning under the conditions of digitalization in higher pedagogical education lies in the fact that relatively independent elements of adaptive learning are considered not in isolation but in their interconnection with others; at the same time, any object is regarded both as a system and as a part of a larger, overarching system.

Within the learner-centered approach, the future teacher begins to evaluate their learning in terms of whether it meets their needs or not. A personal internal evaluation emerges as self-consistency and alignment with one’s own life perspective. As a result, the dominant factor in the organization of education becomes the development of the learner’s personality.

The activity-competence-based approach in the use of adaptive learning under the digitalization of higher pedagogical education focuses on the outcome of learning. Here, the outcome is not considered as the sum of acquired information but as the ability of the future teacher to effectively acquire knowledge in a digital educational environment.

The development of adaptive intelligence contributes to solving key challenges of education digitalization: *Methodological flexibility*: A teacher with a high level of adaptive intelligence easily combines traditional and digital teaching methods. *Motivation formation*: The use of interactive platforms and gamification becomes effective only when the teacher is able to stimulate students’ interest. *Individualization of learning*: The digital environment makes it possible to consider the needs of each student; however, this requires the teacher to have strong analytical and adaptive skills. *Professional self-realization*: Mastery of new technologies opens up opportunities for growth and knowledge exchange within the professional community.

Thus, adaptive intelligence becomes a crucial link between the technical possibilities of digitalization and real educational outcomes.

Ways to Develop a Teacher’s Adaptive Intelligence.

The development of adaptive intelligence can be achieved through: the inclusion of training on emotional resilience and stress management in professional development programs; mastering by teachers of innovative methodologies based on project-based and blended learning; the formation of professional communities for the exchange of digital practice experience; and the promotion of teachers’ research activity in the field of pedagogical innovation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the measures proposed by the authors for improving the educational process of future teachers through the use of adaptive technologies reflect subjective perspectives and the accumulated practical experience of their own teaching activities. The adaptive intelligence of a teacher is a key condition for the successful integration of digital technologies into modern education. It ensures teachers’ readiness for innovation, contributes to the improvement of teaching quality, and fosters the development of students’ critical thinking and motivation. Therefore, the development of adaptive intelligence should become a priority direction in the system of teacher education and professional retraining.

Thus, adaptive learning is considered an effective pedagogical solution that is becoming increasingly popular among modern university instructors. This approach allows future teachers to acquire knowledge in electronic form without relying solely on classroom time, while at the same time making the learning process more individualized for each student.

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